

**Roger Kain, Professor
of Humanities, School
of Advanced Study,
University of London**

Open access book publishing gains momentum

– Roger Kain

Up and coming academics will help create the change needed for open access publishing to gain wider acceptance

Early career researchers in the humanities may still be advised to publish with a traditional press, at least for their first book to help them gain tenure. But attitudes are changing as the academic community realises that open access can result in higher reader numbers, higher citations and more impact.

The next generation will drive change/generational differences

Roger Kain, Professor of Humanities at the School of Advanced Study, University of London, says a big hurdle that needs to be overcome is that senior managers in universities can still lack awareness of open access book publishing. Some view it as self-publishing and therefore of lower quality than traditional publishing. Kain refutes that, saying that open access books usually undergo the same rigorous scholarly processes, such as peer reviews and copy editing.

However, he thinks generational shifts will lead to cultural change.

He said:

“The generation of researchers who were early career five or so years ago and are now coming through to the mid-career stage – they are going to carry a very different view of open access to people of my generation.”

Kain's own experience of open access publishing

Kain is involved in a long-term project with the University of Chicago Press. It's a significant project – a global history of maps and mapping - spanning almost fifty years, multiple authors and more than twenty rounds of public funding. A while ago, Kain says the decision was made to make the research freely available, three years after publication for new books, immediately for those already published.

He said:

“We had started to get comments – ‘is it good that all this public money is put into these wonderful books, this wonderful research, but then it's locked away behind a paywall?’”

Impact of open access publishing

One of the most obvious benefits to open access publishing is higher reader numbers. Kain says there had been 5.6 million hits on the project last time he looked. Some of them have been educators, downloading material and circulating it to students, so Kain is pleased it is being used pedagogically. There has also been an uptick in sales of the printed books since the project went open access.

Fairer access to research and increased collaboration

There are two other major benefits to open access book publishing. It disseminates knowledge and research more widely, making academia more equitable globally. It also encourages academic discourse around research, again on a global level.

Kain said:

“It facilitates conversations around the world. And it breaks down some of the haves and have-nots barriers.”

The use of third party material

That's not to say that open access publishing is without its challenges. Authors regularly encounter problems around images and consent to use third party material. This has been particularly problematic for the project Kain is involved with as there are many, many illustrations in the books – about 1,000 per book.

Kain estimates that for the majority of the images in his book, it was a straightforward process - most libraries and private owners were happy to waive permission costs. Some others asked for a PDF copy of the printed image or a complimentary copy of the hardback book, which retails at \$500 a book. For some, negotiations were more complex, involving detailed licence agreements.

All of this added a lot of time and cost to the project, not least from an administrative perspective. Permission costs were largely covered by private donations; it is common practice in the US for federal dollars to be matched by private dollars.

But, Kain says all the hassle was to be expected for books with so many images. He has no regrets that the decision was made to publish open access, albeit with a delay for the latest volumes.